

THE IMPORTANCE OF SEMIOTICS IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATIONAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF SEMIOTIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract: In this article, about the fields of semiotics and their limits, as well as their types, the importance of semiotic aspects, its application, the necessary pedagogical conditions, the scientists and their views, the branches, directions of semiotics and its use in our daily life. It is mentioned how we can use it.

Key words: Semiotics, primary education, mathematics, semasiology, pragmatics, syntactics.

From the semiotic point of view, it is characteristic to distinguish three levels of research of sign systems corresponding to three aspects of semiotic problems.

Syntax studies the structure of signs and the relationship between them, regardless of what they represent and how they are perceived by the receiver, from the point of view of syntax. Parsing is the processing of text in natural language, the purpose of which is to obtain a syntactic representation of this text, in particular, its syntactic structure.

Semantics studies the relationship between symbols and the objects they denote, regardless of the recipient of the symbols. He studies the general laws of construction of any symbol system considered in syntax. The subject of semantics is defined differently in different semiotic and linguistic concepts. These differences are determined, first of all, by the exact definition of the sign and the idea of the defined reality. Therefore, F. de Saussure understood the sign as a dual essence, which represents the unity of the signifier and the signified (the plane of expression and the

plane of content). Researchers who support this approach see the main task of semantics in studying the relationship between these two sides. There is another idea belonging to Gottlob Frege (1848-1925), according to which it is necessary to distinguish between the objective and semantic meaning of the sign, that is, the signified object and its concept. With such an approach, the main task of semantics is to establish connections between, on the one hand, symbolic expressions, and on the other hand, defined objects and the relationships between them. Semantic analysis is a set of operations that serve to express the meaning of a text in a natural language in the form of writing in some formalized semantic (semantic) language. Semantic analysis models the human process of understanding text.

Pragmatics studies the perception of meaningful expressions of the sign system according to the decision-making ability of the perceiver. Theoretical pragmatics examines hypotheses about the properties and structure of intelligence. Applied pragmatics includes empirical analysis of people's understanding of various linguistic expressions, studies of rhythm and versification, and research devoted to the development of information retrieval systems.

Thus, there are three levels of consideration of any information message. At the pragmatic level, all elements of information exchange are considered to determine the usefulness of information. At the semantic level, abstracting information from the recipient, the ultimate goal of learning is the semantic meaning of the message, its correspondence to the described objects. The narrowest syntactic level is the level of studying only the signs themselves and the relationships between them.

All three levels are important for the application of the semiotic approach in the field of pedagogy and education.

Information around us is often presented in the form of a semiotic system. That is, a set of different types of characters. Its main task is to ensure complete collective and individual communication processes.

So what signs allow him to be like that?

- firstly, any system should be at least integrated.
- secondly, the elements must be systematized according to a certain principle.

- thirdly, new elements can appear only according to a clearly defined principle.

The entire variety of used symbolic tools is a semiotic field. As part of this field, the following main types of signs and sign systems can be distinguished.

- natural;
- functional;
- conditional (conditional);
- iconic;
- oral (natural languages); • signature recording systems.

Natural signs are objects and natural phenomena, if they point to other objects or phenomena and are considered as carriers of information about them. Natural signs -

These are signs of signs, for example, smoke is a sign of fire. To understand natural signs, you need to know what they are and extract the information from them.

Functional signs are things and events that have a direct pragmatic purpose, they are included in human activity and receive information about it. it becomes signs because it walks. These are also signs of signs, for example, production equipment, because it can be a sign that contains information about the entire technical system, which is any mechanism or part element, for example, the teacher's finger ro walking on the list. the number of students in the journal becomes the symbol of the initial request. Functional symbols often have secondary meanings inherent in them by analogy, which is especially evident in superstitions.

Education, where the communication culture of the teacher is a cultural phenomenon, cannot be carried out without paying attention to the culture of the teacher's personality. In the conditions of humanization, one of the main aspects of personal culture becomes the communicative aspect. Successful communication activities contribute to the effectiveness of the teacher as the basis of effective relationships, mutual understanding, self-improvement and elimination of personal crises.

There are several definitions of a teacher's communicative culture:

- pedagogical culture component [1];
- the system of communicative interaction between the teacher and the surrounding world based on a system of signs and symbols [2];
- the quality of communication characterized by the humanistic vector of development [3];
- a set of skills and abilities in the field of communication tools and the laws of interpersonal interaction that help to effectively solve the problems of mutual understanding and communication [4].

When analyzing all definitions, E.V. Sysoeva [5] believes that the teacher's communicative culture can be defined as a set of cultural norms, knowledge, values, skills and abilities used in the communication process and contributing to its effectiveness. To understand communicative culture as an integrative education, the following are important:

- the ability to coordinate and connect one's actions with management;
- receiving and accepting another, choosing and presenting arguments;
- the ability to put forward alternative explanations;
- discuss the problem;
- understanding and respecting the opinions of others;

Be prepared to be flexible and courteous with others.

The level of development of the teacher's communicative culture is reflected in communicative activity.

Communicative activity is a complex multi-channel system of interaction and relations between subjects of the pedagogical process, including: mutual perception; live information exchange; development of a unified communication strategy, decision-making;

It cannot be denied that communication is one of the most important means of control in modern human life. One of its constant elements is the communicative chain of three links "addressee-message-receiver", which allows the transmission of any information. However, A.V. According to Nazarchuk, communication also includes "media reality formed in the process of communication, that is, communicative reality as a separate dimension of social reality" [5]. Thus, communication takes on a slightly different status. Now it is not a simple means of communication, but the way and goal of human existence in culture.

It is impossible to study communication without referring to the theory of signs, because at present there are changes related to increasing the role of sign structures in communicative interactions. New semiotic formations in the form of a system of signs and symbols are created with the help of television, mobile communication, the Internet, etc. This is the unique function of a sign in the formation of a new communicative reality.

Any thought process is based on a sign, therefore, for Charles Peirce (the founder of semiotics), man is a creature that creates signs through semiosis. The relationship of signs is considered from the following position: a sign is something that represents something else in a certain relationship or quality for the interpreter, that is, a sign is impossible without an interpreter. It is this concept that makes it possible to distinguish the "mark" from the "unmarked". In the process of dynamic interpretation of a sign, it does not work until it is perceived as such - semiosis.

There are two main approaches to defining semiosis.

The first is related to the works of Ferdinand de Saussure, where the sign is understood as a double personality, representing the unity of the signifier and the signified. In the semiotic traditions of those times (developed within the framework of structuralism), semiosis is "by establishing a mutual assumption relationship between the form of expression and the form of content - or between the signifier and the signified" [6]. Saussure In linguistics, the postulate of the arbitrariness of the sign is important, in which the connection of the signifier with the signified does not include the specific properties of these components of the sign. order is the process of operation in a system in which its various parts are exchanged. It is the exchange

process that transforms the elements involved into symbols or messages.

The second approach is related to the work of Charles Sanders Peirce, who defines a sign as an object that represents or replaces something else in human activity. To define the concept of semiosis, Peirce uses the triadic scheme "object-sign-interpretor". And if the first two components are clear, then the "interpretor" requires further explanation. For Peirce, an "interpretor" is the way a person uses a sign or the effect a certain sign has on a person. Semiosis is also characterized by the following features:

- subject;
- includes an interpretor - the producer and interpretor of signs appear only in a group of interpreters who know certain rules of interpretation of signs for mutual understanding. The activity of such a group consists of a clear permanent semiosis;

A sign produced by one subject is interpreted by other subjects and produces an interpretant. It already works as another sign, which can also be interpreted. It was found that the (real) object discussed in the group is not expressed directly, but only within the framework of semiosis.

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